

Global metamorphosis of covid19 to AIDS disease from the year 2022

Written by : LAZHAR BENALLAL

ABSTRACT:

Between reality and fiction, the unexpected appearance of SARS-COV2 on a global scale raises several questions about its true origin and what perspective on its long-term evolution.

The problem with the COVID19 weight is that there is no real coordination between scientific researchers from different

disciplines. Indeed missing of exchange of information on SARS-COV2 is almost non-existent between medical experts with physicists, biologists or military and civil specialists in the field of nanotechnology .The technical and scientific report merges all the informations on the problem of finding the best solutions in an unconventional way.This micropublication offers a completely original new approach to the nanomicrobiological description of COVID19 and also new ideas for preventive and curative treatments.

At the beginning of this report :

1- The *description at the nanobiochemical scale* =

*** Formula of the chemical mass integrated in the viral Core = [(59Co₃, O₄) 36+ (C₂, H₅, N) 32+ (C₁₀, H₁₅, N₂, O₈, P) 30].**

*** Genomic formula of the initial recombinant virus = [(GAG POL ENV REV NEF VIF VPR VPX) 9kb + (PDB S1 ~ S2-E-M-N Tmprss2) 20 kb + (PB1) 0.9kb].**

*** Biological and physicochemical properties:**

1- The chemical mass inside the viral core represents a structure composed of multifunctional magnetic nanoparticles in multicomplex form.

2-The chemical structure of the nanometric mass inside the viral core is undetectable by medical electron microscopy but detectable by medical scanner in the form of opaque crystals.

3- Self-multiplication and natural diffusion of the nanometric chemical mass of the viral core in the target cells, causing permanent mutations of the surface glycoproteic spikes whatever the hybrid mutation of the virus.

4- Displacement of the nanometric chemical mass following the resonances of ultrasound caused by various remote sources far from the viral entity (For example = Engines of cars, buses, trucks,

... etc.So it's the true vector of displacement of the virus in the air by magnetic effect, compared to the displacement of viruses via the microdroplets).

5 - Increased capacity of viral multiplication in embryonic environments of human or animal origin (essential biological amplifier for the rapid diffusion of the viral mass).

6-The internal chemical nanoparticles (metallic part) of the viral core are at the origin of hemorrhages or micro-injuries and microtromboses of red-bluish colors in the various blood vessels including the brain.

7-Corona viruses communicate with each other thanks to chemical-magnetic nanoparticles in the viral core and go on the attack if the complementary immune system (C1-INH inhibitors) exceeds 0.5g / liter in plasma.

8- The viral mass goes into a state of temporary hibernation if the intrinsic and / or extrinsic temperature is lower than -16 ° C but its structure is destroyed if the viral mass is exposed to a temperature higher than + 90 ° C. Furthermore, viral multiplication is neutralized if there is no ultrasound or an intermediate booster host (living embryonic mass) or if the level of the C1-INH inhibitor is less than 0.5 g / liter in plasma.

9-The biological and physicochemical structure of the virus shows that it is not of natural terrestrial origin, but rather synthetic and recombinant. The genomic structure and the physicochemical behavior of the whole virus also shows that it is not the result of a short-term artificial manufacturing in a biotechnology laboratory, but rather it demonstrates a complex synthetic form of extraterrestrial origin probably originating from a comet (Meteorite debris rich in fragments of toxic amino acids) from of the solar system.

The first generation of COVID19, which includes Biometalic nanoparticles from extraterrestrial meteorites, are starting to disappear; only the other successive generations of the virus remain which are less pathogenic and which are normal viruses lacking biometric plaques in the middle of the viral core.

10-The new mutant generations of the initial virus are able to affect all human beings of all ages, and the most serious is their new powers to penetrate the living cells of all terrestrial animals and all plants belonging to the terrestrial vegetable kingdom also, even in the absence of external cellular protein receptors of the "ACE2" type.

The interaction of mutant strains of COVID19 with other living animal or plant cells is likely to trigger a new global epidemic in the near future called: "Epidemic Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome : AIDS".

So in literature, molecules known as "female contraceptives", actively participates in neutralizing the excretion of C1-INH inhibitors in hepatic cells, these are two coupled hormonal molecules: ETHINYLESTRADIOL (0.03 mg) + DROSPIRENONE (3 mg) strength per film-coated tablet.

The modulation of the adequate dosages and the duration of the treatment necessary for a correct preventive or curative impact depends on the sex, age and body weight of the individuals. Finally, the use of molecules of chloroquine, Azythromycin, cloves, Bromelina, bicarbonate of soda, vitamin « C », vitamin « D », Zinc,..... or other many substances only decreases the load viral and

does not suppress viral masses in a state of hibernation identical to that of the herpes virus.

In conclusion, the only effective treatment is the third generation female contraceptives applicable for both sexes from the age of 6 years and over.

* PS= Suggestion of an effective medical product ANTI - COVID19 whatever the mutant viral strain: Contraseptive for third generation women (Jasmin) DN , with properties :

C1-INH inhibitor suppressor + Alpha, Beta, Gamma type interferon activator + Diuretic by suppression of pulmonary, hepatic and renal edemas caused by the pathogenic effect of the virus.

With regard to preventive prophylaxis; did you know that 2 vaccinations with an interval of 2 months with an influenza vaccine containing variant strains for the 2020/2021 season or a more recent version of the influenza virus, will give the same protection as any COVID19 vaccine. So a vaccination with its reminder by the influenza vaccine would cause a reactivation of the entire cellular and humoral immune system of any type which will subsequently provide optimal protection both against the seasonal flu and the coronavirus family. This vaccination protocol will protect the human body even against the new variants of coronaviruses which have a particularity of

escaping the “ANTI-COVID19” antibodies, such as the variant serotypes called « Delta » and

« Epsilon » . So in conclusion, there is no difference between influenza and ANTI-COVID19 vaccines with respect to the RNA virus family and with low secondary effects for influenza vaccination compared with the COVID19 vaccin.

The new anti-covid19 vaccine recently developed by the 2 pharmaceutical companies "PFIZER & MODERNA" is very different in its biogenetic composition compared to other vaccines being developed by other pharmaceutical industries in the world. Like GMO vegetal RNA duplicated messenger, The difference with this recent biotechnology industry, is that the other vaccines are composed mainly by fragments of viral antigens or coronavirus fragments integrated on Adenovirus. However, the vaccine manufactured by "PFIZER & MODERNA laboratories" is mainly constituted by fragments of messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) of the virus itself. The composition of this new vaccine represents a real danger for humans in the long term; insofar as this vaccine will play the role of a potential genomic reprogrammer of the entire cell entity to gradually create in Vivo induced pluripotent cells inside living organs. Indeed, the injection of the vaccine will release the interactive genomic fragments of the virus; after which, the exposure of the human being to exogenous electromagnetic micro pulses of antennas belonging to the operators of the mobile telephone; will cause a kind of tissue electroporation; including, the electromagnetic field will open pores at the level of cell membranes and make penetrate a part of the genetic material of protein synthesis of the virus into healthy cells which generates a significant genomic modification with formation of induced pluripotent stem cells foreign to the human body and risk of creating mutant cancer cells, causing sterility and congenital malformations in long-term offspring. This problem is even more serious, since this vaccine is supposed to be administered in 2 doses only 21 days apart.

The last Ultra top secret informations observed shows the use of stealthy American spaceships: "UFO ASTRA- TR3B- Black Triangle" in Algeria (Seen several times at CONSTANTINE

province) and throughout the world for the dispersal in the middle of the night and at low altitude of the masses clouds composed of billions of SARS-COV2 (COVID19) particles. ASTRA TR3B is undetectable by the most sophisticated radars in the world including the S400 and S500. Generally, these spaceships move between 8 p.m. and 10 p.m. They move at low altitude in the form of a squadron made up of 2 ships that stop in atmospheric space between 5 and 10 minutes in the form of small balls. luminous (Takes a lunar shape) then revolve around a very precise circular orbit from the geometric point of view with a diameter of about 1 kilometer then the first spacecraft remains motionless as the second spacecraft takes the north direction of the compass then leaves orbit and this transforms into a black triangle pierced by 3 light sources of a whitish color and at this time this mobile triangular vessel begins to diffuse coronaviruses. In triangular form the TR3B can move at a normal speed but when it turns into a small ball of white light it can move at an incalculable speed. It is serious we must act before it is too late.

At the end of 2021, a new variant of the coronavirus, currently known as the B.1.1.529 variant, appeared in Botswana and South Africa. It contains more than 50 mutations in total with more than 30 changes in the skeletal protein, the researchers said. While many of these mutations were already present in other extant SARS-CoV-2 variants, such as the delta variant, this B.1.1.529 variant could be the winner if awarded the title of "variant with most mutations" today. Seeing so many mutations, especially when they affect a very important prickly protein, should raise some eyebrows. It is possible that the immune protection from a previous vaccination or infection was directed at previous versions of the skeletal protein and virus. This protection has some flexibility and may resist different mutations of the virus to some extent. However, this protection may become less effective as the virus becomes different. The biggest concern is the possibility of a "runaway variant" emerging, completely different from previous versions, and thus easily bypassing the immune protection. There are

unconfirmed reports of infections and cases in individuals who have received the vaccine, but “at this point it is too early to tell anything.” Researchers discovered B.1.1.529 in genome sequencing data from Botswana. The variant stood out because it contained more than 30 changes in a skeletal protein -- the SARS-CoV-2 protein that recognizes host cells and is the main target of the body's immune responses. Several changes were found in variables such as delta and alpha, which are associated with increased infection and the ability to avoid infection-preventing antibodies.

So the extraterrestrial origin of COVID 19 as well as its diffusion in the world by the spacecraft "ASTRA TR3 Black supersonic" will give birth sooner or later to a global pathology of the "AIDS" which would be a real challenge for the scientific researchers of the times modern. By now it has become very clear that the news varies of coronavirus "Omicron" from the month of December 2021 goes from the stage of hibernation inside living animal and plant cells to the symptomatic active stage. either through inexplicable direct or indirect contact with the genetic material of seasonal influenza viruses of serotype "H3N2".

- (*)= ORCID.ID : <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3337-8037>

°Correspondance address : LAZHAR BENALLAL .B.P.49
Massinissa – EL KHROUB – CONSTANTINE 25026 ALGERIA (

DZ)

°Email : dynamonet@protonmail.com

°Tel : +213663236717

°Fax : +13603647498

°WEB : www.benallal.cf